

Studies on Membranes Prepared from Some Sparingly Soluble Inorganic Precipitates held on Parchment Paper

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Parchment membranes impregnated with sparingly soluble inorganic compounds (BaSO_4 , BaCrO_4 , PbSO_4 and PbCrO_4) were prepared. The concentration potential across these membranes were measured in solutions of some 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes of varying concentrations. From these observed potential values other quantities like cationic transport number in the membrane phase (\bar{t}_+), perm selectivities (P_s) and apparent anionic mobilities (\bar{v}) were calculated and the effect of external electrolyte concentrations on these parameters were studied.

THE studies on membrane potential are helpful in understanding the behaviour of membrane. Of various factor governing the membrane potential, fixed charge density, pore-size, adsorption, ionic size and ionic mobilities are of great importance. These factors were discussed thoroughly by a number of workers¹⁻³. The concentration potential across parchment and inorganic precipitate membranes were first studied by Willis⁴ and later by Beg and Pratap⁵ who examined effect of external electrolyte concentration on membrane permselectivity, cationic transport numbers in the membrane phase and apparent anionic mobilities in solutions of certain 2:1 electrolytes. Preparations of parchment supported Barium sulfate membranes⁶ have been reported, but very little work has been done on concentration potentials in solutions of 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes. In this paper membrane potentials were measured across parchment supported barium sulfate, barium chromate, lead sulfate and lead chromate membranes in solutions of 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes e.g., KCl , NaCl , K_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 of varying concentrations. From these potential values cationic transport

number in the membrane phase (\bar{t}_+), membrane perm selectivities (P_s) and apparent anionic mobilities (\bar{v}) are calculated and effect of external electrolyte concentration on these parameter are studied.

Experimental

Parchment paper of vegetable origin after cutting into suitable sizes were affixed at the end of the pyrex glass tubes of internal diameter 5-6 mm with the help of an adhesive obtained by dissolving polystyrene in toluene. After testing for leaks the inside and outside of the tubes were filled by 0.1(M) $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{CrO}_4$ and 0.1(M) $\text{BaCl}_2/\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution respectively. The potential difference generated at 1st moment of contact of the two solutions with the parchment paper was determined by measuring the e.m.f. of the cell.

S.C.E. / Internal solution — Membrane — External solution/S.C.E.

TABLE—1

Membrane	Internal solution	External solution	'b'	E (mv)	Potential attained after 24 hours (mv)
Barium sulfate	K_2SO_4 soln. (0.1M)	BaCl_2 soln. (0.1M)	1.035×10^{-2}	96.60	102.50
Barium chromate	K_2CrO_4 soln. (0.1M)	BaCl_2 soln. (0.1M)	8.4×10^{-2}	11.90	11.20
Lead sulfate	K_2SO_4 soln. (0.1M)	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. (0.1M)	9.15×10^{-2}	109.30	109.00
Lead chromate	K_2CrO_4 soln. (0.1M)	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. (0.1M)	7.05×10^{-2}	14.18	12.40

TABLE 2—RECORD OF THE MEMBRANE POTENTIAL IN MV FOR DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTE AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS. TEMP. = 27±1°

Electrolytes	KCl solution				NaCl solution				K ₂ SO ₄ solution				Na ₂ SO ₄ solution				
	BaSO ₄	BaCrO ₄	PbSO ₄	Em	BaSO ₄	BaCrO ₄	PbSO ₄	Em	BaSO ₄	BaCrO ₄	PbSO ₄	Em	BaSO ₄	BaCrO ₄	PbSO ₄	Em	
Concentration (C ₁) × 10 ⁴ (N)																	
4	32.70	29.10	28.50	26.50	21.00	24.70	32.20	25.80	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
8	29.50	27.50	23.90	24.80	17.30	22.00	29.65	23.80	—	—	34.90	—	—	—	—	—	—
16	25.60	24.50	20.60	20.50	16.00	20.10	25.90	22.10	35.15	—	34.10	34.40	35.15	—	—	—	—
32	21.40	22.80	19.30	19.40	15.50	19.00	21.70	19.80	34.80	34.90	33.30	31.50	34.80	34.90	—	—	—
64	19.00	18.00	15.90	15.40	13.90	16.50	16.90	17.50	31.90	29.95	30.60	30.70	30.20	31.50	34.75	34.80	—
128	16.50	13.15	14.45	14.30	11.60	13.70	13.60	14.40	29.50	27.85	29.60	30.00	27.30	29.10	34.30	33.20	—
256	12.40	7.80	10.35	11.10	9.90	11.90	11.50	11.20	25.30	24.00	26.90	27.90	20.90	22.70	32.70	32.20	—
512	6.80	4.50	8.20	7.70	5.85	7.70	6.10	5.45	21.90	21.20	22.30	22.90	16.50	16.65	30.40	30.75	—
1024	5.20	3.65	5.50	5.10	2.65	3.45	2.10	1.80	19.00	18.10	18.35	18.60	15.00	15.60	28.00	28.50	—
2048	4.30	2.10	3.50	3.05	0.40	0.75	-0.60	-1.05	16.60	16.30	17.60	17.30	12.50	12.80	24.75	24.90	—
4096	3.20	1.20	1.85	1.50	-1.25	-1.30	-2.40	-2.75	15.00	14.35	15.15	15.30	10.80	12.10	21.70	21.50	—
8192	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	14.05	13.75	13.70	13.80	10.20	11.30	19.20	19.40	—

The potential was found to change very rapidly with time and 75-80% of its maximum value was attained within a few minutes. The change of potential with time was recorded.

The change of potential value with time was assumed to obey the empirical relation $E = \frac{t}{a + bt}$ where E

and t are potential of the cell set and time in secs respectively and a and b are two constants. The maximum value of the potential (E_{∞}) was theoretically calculated from the intercept of the linear curve obtained by plotting $1/E$ vs $1/t$. This value was found to be nearly equal to that obtained experimentally after a lapse of 24 hours. The solutions of the two sides of the parchment paper were then interchanged and kept for 24 hours. The results are shown in Table 1.

Membrane potential :

For measurement of the membrane potential the following cell arrangement was used

The solutions on the two sides of membrane were of same electrolyte and the ratio of C_1 to C_2 was always equal to 4. The two sides of the membrane were repeatedly washed with the respective experimental solutions and steady values of cell potentials recorded by means of a Leeds Northrup K_2 type potentiometer with a Leeds Northrup galvanometer were regarded as the membrane potential. Maximum asymmetry potential allowed either for the saturated calomel electrode pairs or for the membrane electrodes was ± 0.1 mv. The membrane potential was measured at $27 \pm 1^\circ$ with an accuracy of ± 0.05 mv.

Results and Discussion

The membrane potentials across the parchment supported $BaSO_4$, $BaCrO_4$, $PbSO_4$ and $PbCrO_4$ membranes in solutions of KCl , $NaCl$, K_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4

are shown in Table 2. The sign of the membrane potential is taken to be the same as that of the electrode dipped in the dilute solution.

The cationic transport number in the membrane phase (t_+) was calculated by using the Kittelberger's equation⁸ which for a 1:1 electrolyte becomes

$$\bar{t}_+ = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{E_m F}{RT \ln (f_1 c_1 / f_2 c_2)} + \frac{1}{2} \dots (I)$$

and for a 1:2 electrolyte it becomes

$$\bar{t}_+ = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{E_m F}{RT \ln (f_1 c_1 / f_2 c_2)} + \frac{1}{3} \dots (II)$$

where E_m is the membrane potential and the other terms have the usual significance. The concentration (C) is expressed in eqivs/litre. The values of 'f' were calculated using Debye Hückel equation⁹.

The perm-selectivity (P_s) of a membrane being a measure of membrane selectivity of the counter ions over co-ions was calculated using Winger's¹⁰ relation

$$P_s = \frac{t_+ - t_-}{1 - t_+} \dots (III)$$

where t_+ is the cationic transport number in the free solutions. The values of t_+ were taken from standard values¹¹⁻¹².

The relative speeds of the anion as well as the probability of the anion entering the membrane pore were determined by its apparent anionic mobility⁴ which was calculated using the relation^{4,8},

$$E_m = \frac{RT}{F} \frac{U/z_+ - V/z_- \ln \frac{f_1 c_1}{f_2 c_2}}{U + V} \dots (IV)$$

Assuming the values of cationic mobility (U) to be the same as that in the free solution the values¹³ for

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

K⁺ and Na⁺ ions were taken to be 73.52 and 50.11 ohm⁻¹ cm² equiv⁻¹ respectively.

The dependence of the values of t_+ , p_s and v for the said membranes on the external electrolyte concentration were shown by plotting their respective values against $-\log C_1$ in Figs. 1-6.

In all the cases membrane potentials were found to decrease with the increase in external electrolyte concentration. This is due to the fact that with increase in external electrolyte concentration more and more cations enter in the pores of the membrane which gradually loses its selectivity. However, the membrane potentials fall more sharply for NaCl solution than for KCl solution and at higher concentration of NaCl the sign of the membrane potentials were found to be reversed. At any concentration the membrane potentials values were higher when sulfates of the same alkali metals were

used in place of their chlorides indicating enhanced selectivities of the membranes towards K⁺ and Na⁺ ions in solutions of their sulfates. This is considered as due to the preferential anion adsorption^{14,15} by the materials of the membranes.

Like the membrane potentials the cationic transport numbers in the membrane phase and perm selectivities of the membranes decreased with increase in external electrolyte concentration for the same reason. However, the values of p_s were not found to be negative within the experimental range of concentration. That is, t_+ is always greater than t_- . It is, therefore, concluded that inspite of increased adsorbed co-ion concentration a complete charge reversal in the membrane phase did not take place.

The increase of apparent anionic mobilities with the increase in external electrolyte concentration can also

be explained on the basis of theories put forward by Willis⁴. An adsorptive layer is formed in the surface of the membrane in contact with an electrolyte solution. Within the membrane there is a diffuse ionic atmosphere starting from its negatively charged walls. At lower concentration the thickness of ion atmosphere being maximum there will be a greater repulsion of the anion from the membrane surface. The anionic mobilities will, therefore, be minimum at this stage. As external electrolyte concentration increases due to the greater co-ion adsorption the ionic atmosphere decreases. This leads to the increase in the values of mobilities.

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